

Basic Knowledge on DCCs

Common information on Digital Calibration Certificates

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Content and goal

- These slides are intended as common introduction to the Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC).
- The purpose is to support the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community by providing basic knowledge on
 - What DCCs are
 - Benefits of creating and using DCCs
- The slides are part of a knowledge compendium also containing more specific information for technical staff, management and stakeholders of NMIs and DIs

What is a Digital Calibration Certificate?

The handling of current calibration certificates requires manual work

- Calibration certificates are commonly still **paper** documents or PDF, Word, Excel files, etc.

These formats work for human readers

- In a digital era, calibration data needs to be read by software and machines in addition to human users
- Transcribing data from a certificate needs to be done **manually**

Vulnerability to human errors that cause risks

Inefficiency in terms of time and costs

What is a Digital Calibration Certificate?

Source definitions: <https://www.gartner.com/en/glossary>

Digital Transformation

Digitize

paper >> image, PDF file,...

Digitization

analogue process >> digital form

Digitalization

digital technologies >> change business models, new revenue

Digital Calibration Certificate

What is a Digital Calibration Certificate?

Basic definition aspects of a Digital Calibration Certificate

- A Digital Calibration Certificate is a machine-readable electronic file providing all information and data that needs to be reported from calibration.
- The information and data in the file is structured in a clear format allowing unambiguous access through software and machines.
- A Digital Calibration Certificate has the same status as a paper-based calibration certificate, but it is enabling an easy integration into digital applications.
- DCC is the abbreviation used for Digital Calibration Certificates in the metrology domain.

What is a Digital Calibration Certificate

Comparing paper-based with digital workflow

>> workflows are the same except for format of certificate

What is a Digital Calibration Certificate?

Creation and use worldwide by

- Humans and machines
- National Metrology Institute (NMI)
- Designated Institute (DI)
- Accredited laboratory
- Non-accredited laboratory
- End-users in various fields such as pharma, manufacturing, science

What is a Digital Calibration Certificate?

DCC2GO survey results

Approximately what percentage of your certificates are in n digital/electronic format?

Have you already started to implement electronic/digital formats and automated processes for calibration in your organization?

When do you plan to use DCC?

Benefits from using DCC

Reduction of paper

McKinsey estimated saving of \$6.5 billion by electronic bill of lading in trade¹

Environment and sustainability

1: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/travel-logistics-and-infrastructure/our-insights/the-multi-billion-dollar-paper-jam-unlocking-trade-by-digitalizing-documentation>

Benefits from using DCC

Availability of electronical (digital) form

Increased efficiency of processes and media break free data streamlining

Meet customer request for electronical formats

Can allow for significantly more information to be provided to customers

Effects visible already by changing from paper to PDF and similar electronical forms.

Benefits from using DCC

Machine-readable & structured data

Reduced human errors at transcription of data

Reduced time in exchange and storage of data, e.g., for ERP systems

Demonstrate compliance with industry standards such as ISO/IEC 17025

Benefits from using DCC

Machine-interoperable content

Advancing services through more sustainable data for automation

Advancing possibilities of data analytics and use of AI (drift detection, ...)

Breaking up “data silos” by data interoperable for humans and machines across domain borders

DCC2GO outline of types of DCCs

Type	Example
Type 0 Electronic file that is only human readable	PDF , Word, Excel (common today)
Type 1 Electronic file that is human readable and has a machine readable appendix	PDF/A-3 file with XML/JSON file included
Type 2 Machine readable electronic file that includes a human readable appendix	XML DCC file including a human readable PDF or HTML file
Type 3 Pure machine readable electronic file	Only XML file (human readable display on-premise)
Type 'future vision' Distributed and interlinked machine readable data rather than a single file	Linking of databases providing definitions of terms in DCCs

Remarks

- This type classification is no maturity ranking. Depending on the intended application one or another type is relevant.
- Type 2 (XML DCC) is implemented by most organisations today who started to work with DCCs.
- Many organisations who can already use PDF, see type 1 as a starting point for a transition to types 2 and 3.
- See DCC2GO material for technical staff for details on type 1 (METAS concept) and type 2 (PTB coordinated DCC).

How do I start working with DCC?

Year One – Preparation and exploration phase

Identification of benefits and challenges of DCCs with aim of defining the scope and requirements for the digital DCC infrastructure needed at the metrology institute and customer side.

Six crucial steps in this phase are to

1. Identify existing DCC technologies.
2. Identified which calibration labs will have the largest benefit of implementing DCC.
3. Identifying which customers will have the largest benefit of implementing DCCs.
4. Identify what implications it will have when implementing DCCs
5. Establishing an initial management strategy for implementation work.
6. Do initial pretest internally and with customers.

The DCC2GO guides are a starting point for this process but should be followed by exploration of available updated digital resources and affiliated developments in the metrology community.

How do I start working with DCC?

Phases in a longer run

Phase 1 - Preparation and exploration

Phase 2 - Implementation and validation

Phase 3 - Dissemination, Training and Maintenance

More details in
management
material

Remarks

- DCC2GO has developed guidelines to provide information on the possible work that can be done for an implementation of DCCs in each of the phases. These guidelines are part of the “DCC2GO Starter-Kit”.
- The phases and work are based on hands-on experience by the DCC2GO project partners from their own work with DCCs. It shall help smaller and emerging NMIs and DIs to start working with DCCs.

„Security“ refers to various aspects of DCC

Most relevant are aspects of a secure transmission of DCCs

- Protection of an electronic file from illegal altering (modification)
- Protection of data from illegal access (encryption)
- Identification of the person and the organization issuing the DCC

Other aspects are

- Ensuring readability by human users and readability in a longer-term of 10 and more years
- Including longer-term storage of electronic files
- Data can securely be accessed and assessed by machines without need for human intervention

Digital signatures,
protected storage, ...

Details @ technical
expert material

More details on next
slides

A common question is if human readability is retained by DCCs

- DCCs can retain a human readable component for backwards compatibility (different DCC types have different ways of making it human readable).
- This could be a PDF file or similar formatted in a way today's paper certificates look alike.
- Humans can read and understand the machine-readable data formatted in XML (and JSON)
- In addition, software is likely to be used in the future to create human-readable views of the DCCs data addressing different needs. E.g., people from accreditation could want to see different information than a customer of a calibration.
- Finally, larger amounts of data could be exchanged through DCCs than with today's paper-based formats and software tools could enable new possibilities to display such data to humans too.

Long term readability of DCC

It is a legal requirement

- ~~• Print the DCC on paper and store it in an archive~~

- **Long term readability of electronic files is established considering two aspects**

- Obtaining and maintaining a data (file) **storage infrastructure that is able to securely keep records of electronic files for a longer period of time**; e.g., an e-file system or similar. Investments are needed to implement the necessary infrastructure.
- Storing data in file **formats where it is likely to have software available in a longer term allowing to read the data**. XML and PDF/A-3 are formats imposing to support long term archiving.
- Resources needed to understand the data (e.g., catalogues with terminology) are also long term readable.

Further aspects of legal requirements in material for management

DCC and Accreditation Authorities

Examples of impact from DCCs on the accreditation process?

- Accreditation regarding ISO/IEC 17025:2018: **DCC as electronic format is acceptable.**
- Assessors can view DCCs with existing standard software (nothing exotic needed); however, **assessors will need to get used to the format and take more time at the beginning** when accessing DCCs for the first time.
- Of course, the process of creating, storing and securing the DCCs in respect to an assessment of the quality management must be properly documented by a laboratory.
- **DCCs create value also for future accreditation:** Checks of ISO/IEC 17025 compliance and requirements could be supported by software and harmonized data structures.
- An accreditation logo on a report could be replaced by an electronic seal from an accreditation body (e.g., DAkkS eAttestation)

Various other aspects of DCCs

People who work with DCCs see further important aspects

- Machine-readability and cross-domain interoperability of DCCs
- Secure transmission of DCCs across European borders and to countries outside Europe
- DCCs in the context of quality management
- Withdrawing DCCs
- Guidance on necessary resources
- Ability to participate in and contribute to committees who develop DCCs

Please visit the following presentations for more specific knowledge

DCC
for
Technical Experts

DCC
for
Management

DCC
for
Stakeholders

Credits

21SCP01 DCC2GO

Supporting the implementation of Digital Calibration Certificates in the European metrology community

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Images on slide 6 (“What is a Digital Calibration Certificate?”)

- Image by Freepik https://www.freepik.com/free-photo/side-view-employee-using-printer-work_32078028.htm
- Image by Freepik https://www.freepik.com/free-photo/standard-quality-control-concept-m_36027725.htm
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